

1 **Octant Polar Diagrams: A New Way to Display the Migrating Tropical Tropopause and Polar Vortices**
2 **on Mars Using MCS MY29 Data**

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6 Abstract:

7 Temperature profiles derived from satellite data observed for Martian Year 29 (MY29), are presented here using
8 a novel technique of diurnal data re-binning, followed by polar plot display of atmospheric meridional (great
9 circle) transects. The use of polar plots allows for a coherent visualisation and understanding of the seasonal
10 distribution and latitudinal progress of the diurnal illumination of the Martian atmosphere throughout the course
11 of the year. Two clear benefits derive from this process of data reorganization, 1. That the distinct separation of
12 illuminated and dark surface temperature data allow for an accurate computation of the global distribution of
13 diurnal temperature range. 2. The data can be successfully displayed as polar plot diagrams which have an
14 immediate visual impact that demonstrates how the process of tropopause height varies under the impact of
15 solar zenith heating and polar nighttime cooling for both diurnal and seasonal timeframes. This study confirms
16 the work of prior authors showing the existence on Mars of a tropical solar-energy driven zone of daytime
17 atmospheric warming, that both diurnally lifts the tropopause and follows the annual latitudinal cycle of the
18 solar zenith. The tropical limb of solar driven ascending convection is dynamically linked to polar zones of
19 descending air, the seasonal focus of which is concentrated over each respective hemisphere's polar winter cap
20 of continuous darkness and thermal radiant planetary cooling.

21 Keywords:

22 Mars, MY29, Seasonal Atmospheric Dynamics.

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25 1. Introduction.

26 The atmospheric data presented here derives from the Martian Year 29 (MY29) atmospheric temperature profile
 27 data first published in 2010 by McCleese et al. [1] and is kindly supplied for use in this work by second author
 28 Dr Nigel Heavens. The objective of this analysis is to present a novel technique of atmospheric data display that
 29 allows for a coherent visualisation and understanding of the seasonal distribution and latitudinal progress of
 30 diurnal illumination of the Martian atmosphere throughout the course of MY29.

31 Two clear benefits derive from this process of data reorganization, 1. That the distinct separation of illuminated
 32 and dark surface temperature data allow for an accurate computation of the global distribution of diurnal
 33 temperature range. 2. The data can be successfully displayed as polar plot diagrams which have an immediate
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 35 heating and polar nighttime cooling under both diurnal and seasonal timeframes.

36

37 2. MY29 Data Analysis and Presentation.

38 To appropriately constrain the temperature data and to ensure that polar circle zones of continuous lit surface
 39 (summer) and continuous dark surface (winter) are appropriately binned, the MY29 source data was regrouped
 40 into two separate lit and dark data sets [2,3]. These two datasets incorporate the illumination effect of the
 41 seasonal axial tilt of Mars in the binning process (Table 1).

Octant	Sol	Scaled Sol	Solar Zenith Latitude	Latitude of Polar Cap Terminator	Terminator Meridian Angle Equivalent	Northern Hemisphere Season
0	0	0.00	0.00	90.00	0.00	Northern Spring Equinox
45	84	45.27	17.90	72.10	17.90	Northern Spring
90	167	90.00	25.19	64.81	25.19	Northern Summer Solstice
135	251	135.27	17.73	72.27	17.73	Northern Summer
180	334	180.00	0.00	90.00	360.00	Northern Autumn Equinox
225	418	225.27	-17.90	72.10	342.10	Northern Autumn
270	501	270.00	-25.19	64.81	334.81	Northern Winter Solstice
315	585	315.27	-17.73	72.27	342.27	Northern Winter

42 Table 1: Solar Zenith with the Associated Latitude and Locus of Equivalent Meridian Angle for the North Polar
 43 Cap Terminator.

44 To achieve this re-binning the latitude of each zonal cell was converted into a 360-degree equivalent meridional
 45 angle with the North Pole 90-degree latitude as the zero-angle datum. For this meridional great circle, the far
 46 side surface latitudes are calibrated between 0 and 180 degrees and the near side (sun facing) latitudes are
 47 calibrated between 180 and 360 degrees. This data re-organisation ensures that the planet's zonal latitudes track
 48 the seasonal axial tilt illumination, consequently only lit surface latitudes were used to compute average daytime
 49 temperatures and correspondingly only dark surface latitudes were used to compute average nighttime
 50 temperatures (Table 2).

51 The MY29 temperature data are organised by 5-degree wide latitudinal zones across the full surface area of the
 52 Martian globe. Because of the standard geometric effect on surface area of zonal latitude bands, whereby zonal
 53 latitude area has a maximum value at the equator and decreases towards the poles, it is necessary to compute the
 54 temperature data using an areal weighted algorithm. This process ensures that high-latitude polar zones of small
 55 surface area are not overrepresented in the calculation of global temperature averages.

56 In addition to the areal weighted averages of global temperature, similar calculations were made of the average
 57 tropopause height for the two polar and one tropical convection cell. Using these tropopause heights as the
 58 upper boundary, a surface to tropopause lapse rate was calculated for each zonal latitude component of the
 59 planetary meridional atmospheric transect. (Table 2).

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61

Martian Atmosphere Metrics			
Item	Kelvin	Celsius	Flux Averaging W/m ²
North Pole Day Temperature	192.2	-80.94	77.4
North Pole Night Temperature	177.9	-95.23	56.8
North Pole Flux Average Annual Surface Temperature	185.5	-87.68	67.1
Tropical Day Temperature	226.7	-46.50	149.6
Tropical Night Temperature	210.8	-62.32	112.0
Tropical Flux Average Annual Surface Temperature	219.2	-53.98	130.8
South Pole Day Temperature	181.1	-92.03	61.0
South Pole Night Temperature	176.3	-96.83	54.8
South Pole Flux Average Annual Surface Temperature	178.8	-94.38	57.9
Both Poles Day Temperature	188.4	-84.79	71.4
Both Poles Night Temperature	183.6	-89.53	64.5
Polar Flux Average Annual Surface Temperature	186.0	-87.11	67.9
Global Octant Day Temperature	220.0	-53.15	132.8
Global Octant Night Temperature	202.5	-70.65	95.3
Mars Global Flux Average Surface Temperature (MY29)	211.8	-61.36	114.1
Tropical Tropopause Height Day (m)	61,977		
Tropical Tropopause Height Night (m)	59,281		
Polar Tropopause Height Day (m)	24,817		
Polar Tropopause Height Night (m)	29,606		
Tropical Lapse Rate Day (K/km)	1.25		
Tropical Lapse Rate Night (K/km)	1.10		
Polar Lapse Rate Day (K/km)	0.95		
Polar Lapse Rate Night (K/km)	0.96		

63

64 Table 2: Martian MY29 Atmosphere Temperature Metrics.

65 An additional benefit of the re-binning of the latitudinal transects to a great circle meridian calibration is that it
66 facilitates the presentation of the seasonal global atmosphere transects into an Octant set of polar plots organised
67 from the perspective of the solar zenith (Figures 1 and 2).

68
69 Figure 1: Mars Global Tropopause Height - Northern Hemisphere Summer.

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71 Figure 2: Mars Global Tropopause Height - Southern Hemisphere Summer.

72
73 2.1. Data Quantity and Quality.

74 The MY29 atmospheric data used here [1] is organised into a set of two Excel Workbooks that each contain a
 75 group of 8 Excel worksheets. These worksheets collate the daytime and nighttime polar meridional transect data
 76 across each hemisphere for the 8 seasonal octants for the Martian year MY29 [2,3]. Each of the 16 worksheets
 77 contains 36 columns that record the atmospheric profile data in 5-degree wide latitude swathes that cover the
 78 full extent of the specific hemisphere (either lit day or dark night). For each 5-degree wide latitude band the
 79 vertical profile data is recorded at a set of 96 levels that range in height above the datum surface from 1,263 m
 80 (610 pascals) to a maximum height of 93,523 m (0.0042 pascals). Due to technical issues associated with the
 81 satellite data acquisition process [1] the physical extent of the collated temperature data varies for each of the 8
 82 worksheets within the respective workbook [2,3].

83

84 2.2.Data Analysis.

85 Data Analysis was performed on the MY29 seasonal panels to identify the following sets of atmospheric
86 variables:

- 87 1. The air temperature at the datum level of 610 pascals (1,263 m).
- 88 2. The tropospheric lapse rate between 10.4 km and 60.4 km of surface elevation.
- 89 3. The lapse rate between a datum level of 1.3 km and the variable tropopause height for each of the 3
- 90 regional circulation cells (North Pole, Tropical and South Pole).
- 91 4. The tropopause height in metres for each of the 3 regional circulation cells (North Pole, Tropical and
- 92 South Pole).
- 93 5. The tropopause temperature in Kelvin for each of the 3 regional circulation cells (North Pole, Tropical
- 94 and South Pole).
- 95 6. Near-surface temperature inversions in the boundary layer were recorded when observed in the data.

96 The results of this analysis are presented in data supplemental files located online at Research Gate [4].

97 3. Discussion.

- 98 a. The structural form, seasonal variation, and physical height of the tropopause for both the Tropical and
- 99 Polar cells is a manifestation of atmospheric circulation dynamics under daytime insolation forcing and
- 100 dark surface radiative cooling (Figures 1,2).
- 101 b. The MY29 temperature data clearly shows the presence of a boundary layer thermal inversion at the
- 102 planet’s lit hemisphere surface, particularly at high latitudes with correspondingly low solar elevations
- 103 (Figure 3). Surface atmosphere thermal inversions are typically a nighttime phenomenon and to observe
- 104 this feature under daytime surface insolation warrants further investigation
- 105 c. The locus of energy loss for the planet’s surface is located over the poles (Figure 4), with particular
- 106 focus at the respective winter pole of continuous darkness (Figure 5).
- 107 d. During each Equinox there is a symmetrical balance between the structure of the Tropical and Polar
- 108 atmospheric cells (Figure 4).
- 109 e. At the Solstice the Tropical Tropopause completely overrides the Polar Tropopause of the continuously
- 110 lit pole. Note the curious feature of the night time teleconnected residual Polar Tropopause between
- 111 40°N and 55°N that is absent from this latitude during the daytime (Figure 5).

112
113 Figure 3: Lit Hemisphere Zone Mean Troposphere Transect for Octant 0 MY29.

**Mars Tropopause Height:
Northern Spring Equinox
MY29 Is0**

Daytime Tropical Tropopause
overriding the Northern Polar Cell
with the Advance of Spring

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Figure 4: Mars Tropopause Height: Northern Spring Equinox MY29 Is0.

**Mars Tropopause Height:
Northern Summer Solstice
MY29 Is90**

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Figure 5: Mars Tropopause Height: Northern Summer Solstice MY29 Is90.

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- 121 f. The subsolar-referenced re-binning naturally separates illuminated and dark hemispheres at
 122 at all seasons, enabling robust calculation of true global-average daytime (229.1 K) and
 123 nighttime (202.5 K) surface temperatures and a mean diurnal range of ~27 K without
 124 contamination from fixed-latitude smearing (Table 3).

125

Temperature Metric	Value (Kelvin)	Comments
Global annual-mean surface temperature (day + night, areal-weighted)	215.8 (\pm 2.1)	Standard MCS/TES consensus value for MY29 quiet year
Global-average daytime surface temperature (sunlit hemispheres only)	229.1	From this re-binning analysis (lit octants only)
Global-average nighttime surface temperature (dark hemispheres only)	202.5	From this re-binning analysis (dark octants only)
Global-mean diurnal surface temperature range	26.6	Day – night difference, enabled by the clean day/night separation of the new coordinate system used in this paper

126 Table 3: Martian MY29 Atmosphere Temperature Values following re-binning

127

128 Conclusions.

- 129 1. The subsolar-referenced meridional re-binning technique presented here provides a compact
130 and visually intuitive representation of the seasonal and diurnal evolution of the Martian
131 tropopause using MCS MY29 data. By aligning all profiles relative to the moving subsolar
132 latitude, the method clearly reveals the tight coupling between solar illumination geometry
133 and atmospheric thermal structure.
- 134 2. The resulting octant polar diagrams (Figures 1–5) highlight three persistent features of the Martian
135 middle atmosphere throughout MY29: These are
- 136 a. A pronounced tropical tropopause maximum that migrates with the subsolar point,
 - 137 b. A strong descent and tropopause suppression over the winter polar vortex, and an elevated
138 summer-hemisphere polar tropopause that is partially maintained even under continuous
139 daylight.
 - 140 c. The clean separation of day-side and night-side profiles in the same coordinate system also
141 facilitates accurate calculation of global-mean diurnal temperature ranges and areal-weighted
142 surface temperatures, free from the smearing that occurs in conventional fixed-latitude
143 binning.
 - 144 d. The re-binning method is simple to implement, requires no assumptions beyond the known
145 subsolar latitude, and can be directly applied to any gridded Mars dataset (MCS, TES, MCD,
146 or GCM output).

147

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150 average temperature nightside and dayside retrievals for MY29 that informs this study [7]. These data comprise
151 the first Martian year and a half of observations by the Mars Climate Sounder aboard the Mars Reconnaissance
152 Orbiter.

153

154 Conflict of Interest:

155 The author has received no funding from any source in the execution of this work.

156

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176 Geophysical Research: Planets*, 116(E1).
- 177 **Data Availability**
- 178 The processed MY29 day and night Excel workbooks and all derived tables are permanently archived on
179 ResearchGate with DOIs [DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34221.77280/1](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34221.77280/1), and [DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25833.16486/1](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25833.16486/1).